

About methods of teaching visual means of the Uzbek language to Russian groups

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RESUME

At present, it is important to strengthen the status of the statehood of the Uzbek language, its study at the world level. This article discusses the use of means of speech expressiveness of the Uzbek language. Tropes and figures have different functional activity in different spheres of communication. They are mainly used in fiction and journalism.

Keywords: means of speech expression, tropes, figures, personification, communication, linguistics

ANNOTATION

Improving the quality and position of the Uzbek language as the official language, strengthening the official language status, and elevating it to the level of developed languages of the world are one of the most pressing issues. This article talks about the use of figurative means of the Uzbek language. Tropes and figures are mainly used in artistic and journalistic literature. Knowledge of figurative means creates a

foundation for students to learn and strengthen the Uzbek language as a state language.

In recent years, our country has been working to radically improve the teaching of the language of the state language in higher education institutions.

" Our main task is to create the necessary conditions for young people to demonstrate their well-being,... to educate and educate the minds of young people on the basis of enlightenment¹."

PF-60 of January 28, 2022 concerning the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, PF-6108 of November 6, 2020, "On measures to improve the fields of education and science during the new development of Uzbekistan," PF-5712 of April 29, 2019, "Confirmation of the concept of developing the National Public Education System by 2030" decrees, April 20, 2017, PQ-2909, "On measures to improve the public education system", Implementation of the tasks set out in the decisions of The Ministry of Higher Education and other policy-making documents of June 15, 2018, "Additional measures to improve the quality of education in higher education institutions and ensure their active participation in the broader reforms undertaken in the country" it requires great responsibility from every teacher-pedagogue.

There are various methods of language teaching, by including them in exercises that prepare language tools for communication, or it is desirable to teach language tools together with communication from the initial stages of language acquisition.

¹ President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev speaks at the 72nd session of the General Assembly of the United Nations Organization (electronic source) <http://uza.uz/oz/politics/zbekiston-prezidentishavkat-mirziyeev-bmt-bosh-assambleyasi-20-09-2017>

As a result of studying the literature on this issue, each pedagogue bases his typology of exercises and tasks, distinguishing among them the most effective ones. It is necessary to choose a specially organized system of exercises and tasks aimed at the development of speech in order to effectively acquire speech in a foreign language and master speech material. E.I.Passov distinguishes the following exercises in his classification: exercises related to language, exercises that form translation skills, speech, question-and-answer, constructive. First of all, the main requirements for the development of the system of exercises for teaching visual language courses to Russian-speaking students are formulated. These requirements can include the following: national mentality; compliance with the communicative goal; The introduction of language tools is sequential; Existence of Tatarit-educational values.

The specific features of teaching visual means of the language determine the specific typology of exercises determined by their linguistic features. In general, these exercises can be divided into language-related and communicative exercises (in scientific literature they are also called communicative-situational). Language exercises are the first step towards improving the vocabulary of the language being studied. For Russian-speaking students, it is necessary to strengthen the theoretical information provided by using specific language exercises after learning the visual means of the Uzbek language. This process is used in the initial stage of teaching the Uzbek language. By means of language exercises, students connect and remember the figurative means of the language, i.e. pictures and figures, and also try to use them in language exercises and speech. These exercises encourage the use of figurative language tools in speech practice. Among such exercises, it is possible to include the tasks related to recognizing and defining the visual means of the language in the contemporaneous language, and translating them into the native language.

In accordance with these goals, it is necessary to implement a special exercise on the visual means of the Uzbek language based on the selected teaching and speech material of the language, and not to exceed the limits of the hours allocated for this subject, specified in the curriculum and program. Initially, it is not appropriate to teach only skills in a higher education institution that focuses on language teaching. However, based on the data obtained during the research, we came to the conclusion that if Russian-speaking students use not only figures, but also figures, the effectiveness of learning the visual means of the language will increase.

However, it is important not to forget that the main goal of Russian language students to learn Uzbek is to be able to communicate freely with those who speak this language. For this purpose, exercises that develop students' communication skills are of great value. Communication requires the practical use of language. This kind of attitude towards the target language makes education a very interesting and attractive process, because it corresponds to the final goal, which is to know the official language.

Communicative exercises cover speaking skills that include:

- use of speech that provides the conditional goal of the speaker's speech activity;
- the situational relevance of the exercises, that is, it is literally attributed to each communication situation as a system of interactions between interlocutors;
- the presence of communication in each phrase.

In order to successfully adapt the educational process to real life, it is necessary to set the conditions of real speech communication in the classroom. It is suggested to work with texts in order to develop skills and abilities to recognize and find TTVs. The following requirements are imposed on the texts intended for work in the audience:

- elimination of the complexity of understanding;
- Grammatical-Lexical Material of the Study Subject;
- Aesthetic value of speech;
- effectiveness that helps to better understand the text and activates the assimilation of the studied educational information;
- educational importance of speech;
- Subject-Man Compatibility.

The means of artistic expression are diverse and numerous. These metaphors are: epithets, similes, animations, representations through symbols, exaggeration, litota, allegory, metaphor, etc. And stylistic figures: anaphora, epiphora, gradation, parallelism, rhetorical question, not fully expressing the idea, but only hinting, etc.

Trope is figurative use of words and phrases to create an artistic image. There are two types of tropes: simile and simile.

Animating is one of the most common types of power, and it is the representation of human characteristics by inanimate and real things, in a godly proportion. Animation is mostly found in fiction. For example may refer to:

Exercise 1. Find the animation from the given examples and explain the meaning.

At noon the weather suddenly changed. The rays of the shining sun disappeared. The dark clouds over the distant mountain peaks veiled his blue face. Then the rain started.

When Ghulamjon entered the village after passing the narrow and steep roads with a thousand pains, darkness surrounded him. The river Pskom, flowing along the edge of the courtyard, roared furiously, its waves splashed into the blue. (Dadakhan Nuri "Guest")

Exercise 2. Find figurative language tools from the given examples and explain their meaning.

With the end of winter and the beginning of the first month of spring, a warm wind blows from above along the coast, and within a week, it swells the buds of grass and trees. On the branches of the willows in Kaynarsoy, beads appear like roasted pistachios. Water rushes to the branches of the tree, blackened by the winter cold, and it becomes as gentle and attractive as the fingers of grown-up girls. The client's lighter almonds are the first to bloom and show their beauty.

If you happen to be in Bogistan at this time, you can't help but admire the skillful art of nature.

Especially at the end of April, when the mountains are covered with green clothes and the red tulips shine like a crystal glass in the sunlight, the interest of this place is very small. (Dadakhon Nuri "Guest")

Conclusion

A distinctive feature of the proposed set of exercises is that the student begins to consciously actively participate in solving the task set before him from the initial stages of mastering the visual means of this or that language. In the process of performing a set of exercises, the opportunity to freely choose linguistic means to express one's thoughts in the Uzbek language is provided. As a result of the exercises, the final product of the speech is created independently by the student, enriched with visual aids.

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